

The presented zoning approach aims to identify sub-regional variability within vineyard landscapes of the Upper Galilee region in Israel.

The zoning was based on the comparative interpretation of existing soil- landscape datasets relevant to vineyard conditions, vine behavior and wine style.

Boundaries were delineated according to observed spatial changes in natural conditions, including relief, slope exposure, soil characteristics, and broader environmental patterns potentially influencing vineyard conditions.

At the current stage, the map represents a conceptual and partly schematic framework intended as a basis for further GIS-based refinement and validation.